

Hmong Christianity

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Hmong communities have been converting to Christianity (primarily Protestant denominations but also Catholic to a lesser degree) across different parts of Southern China, Southeast Asia and worldwide diasporas since the turn of the 20th Century, often entire villages and clans at once. This data entry is primarily focused on Southeast Asia, based on the author's extensive fieldwork in Vietnam. Hmong Christians in China and US diasporas faced different socio-economic contexts, but share enough religious common ground to justify representing them in this single entry. There are also hundreds of thousands of Christians among the 'Miao' national minority of China, of which the Hmong are just a subgroup. While this diverse national minority shares some cultural and linguistic traits, most Miao Christians belong to other subgroups which are mutually unintelligible with Hmong language.

Date Range: 1900 CE - 2018 CE

Region: Hmong-Miao speakers in Southern China, Southeast Asia and the US and French diasporas

Region tags: Southeast Asia

The majority of Hmong speakers are spread across the highlands of Vietnam, Laos, Thailand and China. In USA, Hmong communities are concentrated in St. Paul/Minneapolis, Madison Wisconsin, California and North Carolina. The French diaspora is much smaller, scattered around Paris and a few other urban centres. There are very few Hmong Christians among the Australian diaspora.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Pollard, Samuel (1919) "The Story of the Miao", London: Henry Hooks.
- Source 2: Barney, George Linwood (1957) "Christianity and Innovation in Meo Culture: A Case Study in Missionization," University of Minnesota PhD Thesis.
- Source 3: Ngo, Tam T. T. (2016) "The New Way: Hmong Protestantism in Vietnam", Seattle: University of Washington Press.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://newbooksnetwork.com/tam-t-t-ngo-the-new-way-protestantism-and-the-hmong-in-vietnam-u-washington-press-2016/>
- Source 1 Description: Podcast with Dr Tam Ngo, author of "The New Way" (see above)
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.febc.org/the-lambs-book-of-life>
- Source 2 Description: Evangelical radio ministry's perspective on Hmong conversion
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.hmongstudiesjournal.org/-hmong-religion-religious-beliefs-and-christianity.html>
- Source 3 Description: List of academic articles related to Hmong Religion and Christianity

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.bible.com/en-GB/bible/1269/JHN.1.hmowsv>
- Source 1 Description: Hmong-language Bible

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Hmong word used for Christianity in Asia is "the new way" (kev cai tshiab), in contrast to traditional Hmong religion which converts refer to pejoratively as the "old way" (kev cai qub).

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Hmong Christians seek to convert their ethnic comrades, conversely new Hmong

Christians sometimes face considerable hostility and pressure to renounce their faith from traditional religious leaders (often with the support of local authorities in the cases of Vietnam and Laos).

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

Notes: In general Protestant conversion has entailed a sharp rejection from the "old way" of traditional Hmong culture/religion; new converts burn their family altars, stop partaking in cultural festivals, even stop using traditional musical instruments, etc. On the other hand, Hmong Catholics have proved more accommodating of many aspects of traditional culture.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: In Vietnam and Laos, traditional Hmong religion is supported (and sometimes enforced) by local authorities who see Christianity as a potential threat to stability; conversely, growing Christian influence among the Hmong has some financial backing from both national and transnational evangelical networks.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: In China, Vietnam and Laos there have been numerous cases of local authorities and traditional Hmong leaders persecuting new converts by means of arrest, fines, beatings, confiscation of property, forced renunciations, and so on. This caused thousands of Hmong Christians to migrate to other areas or even other countries and seek asylum (in Bangkok, for instance).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Hmong Christians consider the their wider ethnic group's fortunes (and even survival) to be largely dependent on the extent to which they convert to Christianity.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: All Christians are strongly encouraged to spread the Gospel

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

Notes: All Christians are strongly encouraged to spread the Gospel

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

Notes: One significant trend is Hmong Christians from the US diaspora 'returning' to Southeast Asia for missionary work in what Tam Ngo (2016) describes as "remittances of faith and modernity".

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Notes: Hmong Christians in Vietnam have been accused of discrediting traditional Hmong religion as a means by which to persuade people to convert, which is confrontational but not coercive. On the other hand, when Hmong refugees first reached USA, there were rumors that at least one church pressured refugees into attendance, baptisms, and financial contributions, apparently by implying that it could influence welfare payments.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: On the contrary, Hmong Christianity in Vietnam and Laos has been fiercely opposed by central and local political forces.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Notes: Those who abandon Christianity and return to traditional Hmong religion may be shunned or stigmatised by the Christian community.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 500000

Notes: N.B. This estimate is a very shaky approximation based on limited information: - Vietnam: 3-400,000 (including 45,000 in the Central Highlands) - USA: 70,000 - Laos: 20,000 - France: 15,000 - China: 10,000 - this figure is just among speakers of dialects which are mutually intelligible with Hmong speakers in Southeast Asia and beyond. If we include other subgroups of the 'Miao' national minority in Yunnan and Guangzhou which share broader cultural-historical similarities with the Hmong, then there are other large Christian populations (e.g. over 300,000 A Hmao Christians) which have not been included in this population estimate.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 15

Notes: N.B. This estimate is a very shaky approximation based on limited information: - Vietnam: 30% - USA: 30% - Laos: 4% - France: 10% - China: ? (also see above note)

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (not related to larger religious group)

Notes: In Vietnam and USA, Christianity may become the majority religion of the Hmong in the future.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: Regional hierarchies and structures depend on the denomination (Christian Missionary Alliance, Baptists, Lutheran, Mennonites, Presbyterian, Christian Fellowship Church of Vietnam etc.); in one region, many denominations can be operating and are sometimes in competition with each other.

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– Field doesn't know

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Field doesn't know

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– Yes

Notes: It seems probable that the local congregation would be involved in choosing the leader, but this decision would then need to be approved by higher denominational leaders

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible has been translated in Hmong using the Romanized Popular Alphabet (RPA), created by missionaries in the 1950s

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: From the 1980s until fairly recently, the way by which most Hmong Christians in Vietnam and Laos learnt scripture was through the Far East Broadcast Company (FEBC) Hmong-language radio broadcasts, both because physical Bibles were unavailable and also many people were illiterate.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: According to a traditional legend, the Hmong used to have their own script which was unfortunately lost long ago while the Hmong fled from Han invasion of their lands. Lack of text was seen as a marker of ethnic inferiority, and, thus, to have the Bible written in their own language is now a source of prestige and greatly valued by Hmong communities.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Church leaders and pastors aspire to train at Bible schools in Hanoi, Ho Chi Minh City or abroad in Chiang Mai, China etc.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: In the USA, a few large congregations have built 'megachurches' such as the Saint Paul Hmong Alliance Church. In Asia, Hmong Christians also have aspirations for prestigious church buildings, however their relative poverty and state restrictions mean most churches are small and basic.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: When Hmong Christians from the US diaspora 'return' to Southeast Asia for missionary work, they usually visit specific locations where it is believed many Hmong people died in past times; this can be seen as a pilgrimage of sorts.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (rare)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

Notes: Referred to as Heaven

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

Notes: Referred to as Hell

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in “other” space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Attendees are not supposed to cry or mourn at Hmong Christian funerals, but rather be happy and sing praise songs - since the deceased is believed to be much happier in Heaven.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Most Hmong Christians hve fairly orthodox theological beliefs (God as omnipotent, trinitarian etc.)

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: God is believed to be omniscient

- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: The Bible is believed to be the primary way of God's communication with people; additionally, Hmong Christians in Vietnam believe God used the FEBC (Far East Broadcasting Company) radio broadcasts to communicate with them.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Christians believe that all spiritual manifestations of traditional Hmong religion (ancestors, spirits etc.) are oppressive, demonic spirits which must be driven out in Jesus' name. Angels are believed in but generally not given much precedence.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus is considered to be the human incarnation of God (see notes on the supreme high god)

↳ Does the religious group possess a pantheon of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Premarital sex is also forbidden and polygamy is discouraged

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: Hmong Christians are expected to be hardworking and productive.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Traditional Hmong shamanist practices are considered to be sorcery and therefore forbidden.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: Obedience to parents and clan leaders is encouraged, however non-Christian elders can be disobeyed if they request Christians to partake in traditional practices or ceremonies.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: 'proper ritual observance' refers primarily to church attendance, prayer, reading scripture etc.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: Christian rituals being holy communion, baptism, etc.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: Among church leaders teach about the importance of cleanliness, personal hygiene and house 'orderliness'

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: God will judge sinners in the afterlife, but may also punish sinful behaviour in this life.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Demons can torment those who do evil

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: 'You reap what you sow' principle is also in effect

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: According to one Hmong pastor in Vietnam, Christians who don't tithe honestly may be unsuccessful in their livelihoods activities.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: One prominent Hmong elder in Vietnam who opposed Christianity and cursed believers suddenly fell ill and died; this was seen as divine judgement.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
– No

↳ Other [specify]
– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:
– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
– Yes

Notes: 'You read what you sow' principle

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:
– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– No

Notes: Hmong Christians in Asia are often discriminated or persecuted for their faith, so do not expect social stability.

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Notes: Praying to, and relying on God is believed to result in physical healing.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Hmong Christian messianism borrows from traditional millenarian legends about a former Hmong kingdom in China which was defeated by the Han, and the promise of the return of a Hmong king who would restore the fortunes of the Hmong.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: However, throughout Hmong Christianity in China, Vietnam and Laos, predictions have been made about the time and place of the messiah's imminent return, resulting in large religious gatherings to await the arrival. The most recent major event was in Muong Nhe, Vietnam in 2011.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

Notes: The messiah is expected to establish the kingdom of heaven, which is sometimes conflated with the desire for the Hmong to have their own independent kingdom.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: The messiah will also judge the earth, punish evildoers and restore social justice to the oppressed (namely, Hmong Christians who suffer from poverty and persecution)

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Notes: When Hmong men with multiple wives first converted, they were not required to break up their family; however, polygyny is much less common in recent times.

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Men and women are expected to stay celibate until marriage

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Men and women are expected to stay celibate until marriage

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Hmong Christians may pray and fast for a special occasion, however this is not compulsory

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Hmong Christians are not allowed to consume raw pig's blood, which is considered an important food for traditional Hmong feasts, neither do they eat food which has been offered up to ancestral or other spirits beforehand. Christians are also strongly encouraged to quit drinking alcohol completely, which again makes it difficult for men to socialise with Hmong non-Christians.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily

alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:

– No

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: Christians are required to destroy the household altar upon conversion; former shamans must destroy their religious equipment.

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Hmong Christians are expected to attend church meetings on a Sunday and 'keep the Sabbath' (i.e. do no work on Sundays); other mid-week meetings are optional.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: Occasionally in Vietnam and Laos, new Christian converts have been arrested and beaten up by hostile local authorities; however, at present this is the exception rather than the norm.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Apart from the standard Biblical principles (e.g. Ten Commandments), most Hmong Christians accept the following extra precepts: 1) Love God as you love your parents, love your parents as you love God 2) No alcohol, no dog meat, no blood soup 3) No premarital sexual relations 4) No adultery or polygyny 5) No stealing 6) No fighting or arguing 7) No gambling 8) No smoking addiction 9) No improper or offensive speech, no swearing, no singing traditional folk songs 10) No offerings to spirits, no divination

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: This is not necessary or desired, but in practice Hmong Christians often face marginalisation by other villagers - until the Christians become the majority, at which point out-members sometimes become marginalised!

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private,

household):

– Yes

Notes: Many church groups meet on Sundays in believers' homes, either in order to keep a low profile or because they don't have the funds for a church building.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 100

Notes: This figure is perhaps the smallest by which a Hmong Christian community can afford to build a church building; some church meetings have up to 300 regular attendees.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Notes: Ideally, pastors are trained at Bible schools - but in practice, the majority of church leaders have no training and are therefore not official pastors.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: Among Christian believers usually refer to each other as brothers and sisters, implicitly undermining traditional clan hierarchies.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

- A tribe

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

- Yes

Notes: Most Hmong churches provide this service locally, whereby church members pool together and donate food supplies to the afflicted.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Yes

Notes: Modern states provide this support; however, Hmong Christians in China at the turn of the 19th century had no state support.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

- Yes

Notes: The scale of poverty relief varies from church to church, ranging from informal resource pools to more organised poverty assessments and development projects (i.e. road-building) through communal labour.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Yes

Notes: Modern states provide this support (very limited in Laos); however, Hmong Christians in China at the turn of the 19th century had no state support.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

- Yes

Notes: Most Hmong churches provide this service locally, whereby church members pool together and donate food supplies to the afflicted.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Modern states provide this support (except in Laos); however, Hmong Christians in China at the turn of the 19th century had no state support.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Hmong Christians in Asia study theology at denominational Bible Schools in Hanoi, Ho Chi Minh City, Chiang Mai or China.

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: Despite a reasonable number of Hmong women who study theology, at present official pastors are exclusively male; upon finishing their studies, women tend to become evangelists, musical worship leaders or small group leaders.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Modern states in Asia provide conventional education, however in Vietnam and Laos Hmong Christians are discriminated against and are rarely able to obtain university scholarships.

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherent's interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Many Hmong church groups have faced difficulty registering their churches in Vietnam and Laos institutional bureaucracies, who do not want to legally acknowledge their presence.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Regular tithes of 10% on income (or rice, if no cash income is earned) are expected from - but not enforced on - Hmong Christians. Hmong pastors in Vietnam complain that tithes collected are not enough to support a salary for ministers.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In practice, most Hmong Christians in Laos and Vietnam do not have to pay tax due to their extremely low incomes.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Hmong Christians are practically excluded from almost all salaried government positions, including the army.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Notes: Various Hmong-Miao scripts (Pollard script, RPA etc.) were originally devised by Western missionaries in order to translate the Bible, however the RPA is now used by the wider Hmong community and not exclusively for religious purposes.

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Vietnamese and Laotian governments have both created Hmong scripts based on their own scripts, however Hmong Christians don't use them for religious material.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: Annual festivals celebrated by Hmong Christians include Christmas, Easter, Thanksgiving day and Valentine's Day.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: Most Hmong in Vietnam and Laos still achieve semi-sufficiency, growing their own rice and maize as well as cash crops for trade. In Thailand and China, Hmong communities are still largely rural but more likely to be involved in large-scale agriculture and more reliant on the cash economy.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No